

**“ИЖТИМОЙ-ИҚТИСОДИЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШДА
ИННОВАЦИОН МЕНЕЖМЕНТ: МУАММО ВА ЕЧИМЛАР”**

**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ
ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ
ТОШКЕНТ МОЛИЯ ИНСТИТУТИ**

**“ИЖТИМОЙ-ИҚТИСОДИЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИ КНИ
ТАЪМИНЛАШДА ИННОВАЦИОН МЕНЕЖМЕНТ:
МУАММО ВА ЕЧИМЛАР”**

**“ИННОВАЦИОННЫЙ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТ В
ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ
СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ”**

**“INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN MAINTAINING
SOCIO-ECONOMIC STABILITY: PROBLEMS AND
SOLUTIONS ”**

**МАВЗУСИДА ХАЛҚАРО ИЛМИЙ-АМАЛИЙ АНЖУМАН
МАТЕРИАЛЛАРИ ТЎПЛАМИ**

11 НОЯБРЬ 2022 ЙИЛ

**ТОШКЕНТ
“IQTISOD-MOLIYA”
2022**

ISBN 9789943-13-999-7

9 784531 1321322

**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ
ОЛИЙ ВА ЎРТА МАХСУС ТАЪЛИМ ВАЗИРЛИГИ
ТОШКЕНТ МОЛИЯ ИНСТИТУТИ**

**“ИЖТИМОЙ-ИҚТИСОДИЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИКНИ
ТАЪМИНЛАШДА ИННОВАЦИОН МЕНЕЖМЕНТ:
МУАММО ВА ЕЧИМЛАР”**

**“ИННОВАЦИОННЫЙ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТ В
ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ
СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ”**

**“INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN MAINTAINING
SOCIO-ECONOMIC STABILITY: PROBLEMS AND
SOLUTIONS ”**

**МАВЗУСИДА ХАЛҚАРО ИЛМИЙ-АМАЛИЙ АНЖУМАН
МАТЕРИАЛЛАРИ ТЎПЛАМИ**

11 НОЯБРЬ 2022 ЙИЛ

**ТОШКЕНТ
“ИҚТИСОД-МОЛИЯ”
2022**

УЎК: 338.2

КБК: 65.05

**Тақризчилар: Академик С.С.Гулямов
и.ф.д., проф. Т.Т.Жўраев**

Тошкент молия институти Кенгашининг 2022 йил 29 ноябрдаги 4-сонли йиғилишнинг 5.2-сонли Қарори асосида чоп этишга тавсия этилган. –Т.: ТМИ., 2022. – 1039 б.

и.ф.д., проф. Т.З.Тешабаевнинг умумий раҳбарлиги остида

Таҳрир ҳайъати аъзолари: проф. С.Мехмонов, доц. А.Исламкулов, доц. Ш. Синдаров проф. А.Пардаев, доц.Ғ.Сафаров, проф.Э.Набиев, проф.Ф.Назарова, доц.Ш.Аллаяров ва “Менежмент ва маркетинг” кафедрасининг барча профессор-ўқитувчилари.

Ушбу илмий маъруза тезислари тўпламида ижтимоий-иқтисодий барқарорликни таъминлашда инновацион менежментдаги муаммо ва уларни бартараф этиш бўйича аниқ ечимлар, шунингдек мамлакатимиз ҳамда хорижий йирик иқтисодчи олимлар, тажрибали амалиётчилар, олий ўқув юртларининг профессор-ўқитувчилари, илмий тадқиқот институтлари ва марказларининг етакчи илмий ходимлари, докторант ва мустақил изланувчиларнинг илмий тадқиқот иши натижалари мужассамлашган.

Ушбу нашрда келтирилган барча маълумотлар ва фикр-мулоҳазалар муаллифларга тегишли бўлиб, таҳрир ҳайъати аъзоларининг фикрига мос келмаслиги мумкин. Нашрда келтирилган рақамлар, статистик маълумотлар, фикр-мулоҳазалар учун муаллифлар масъул ҳисобланади.

УЎК: 338.2

КБК: 65.05

ISBN 978-9943-13-999-7

**© Тошкент молия институти, 2022
© “IQTISOD-MOLIYA”, 2022**

2. Казначеева, С. Н., Челнокова, Е. А., Коровина, Е. А. *Агротуризм как одно из перспективных направлений индустрии туризма // Международный журнал прикладных и фундаментальных исследований, № 3, 2017, с. 252.* [URL: <http://rrbusiness.ru/journal/article/1243/>].

3. Крутиков, В. К., Федорова, О. В., Гворыс, В. *Развитие сельского туризма: преодоление инерции торможения (анализ отечественного и зарубежного опыта) // Российское предпринимательство, № 23 (245), 2013, с. 98.*

4. Н. В. Зайцева, И. Н. Кандричина. *Туризм на сельских территориях: перспективный бизнес с сохранением историко-культурного наследия// журнал Труды БГТУ. , 2020 г, Серия 6, № 1, с.-78.*

5. Беларусь Республикаси миллий статистика қўмитаси
Электрон манба: <http://dataportal.belstat.gov.by/Indicators/Preview?key=205625>

6. Беларусь Республикаси миллий статистика қўмитаси
Электрон манба: <http://dataportal.belstat.gov.by/Indicators/Preview?key=205626>

7. <https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20210323005538/en/Global-Agritourism-Market-2021-to-2027---by-Activity-Sales-Channel-and-Region---ResearchAndMarkets.com>

8. *Отпуск в белорусской деревне [Электрон манба]. – манба ҳаволаси:* <https://learngerman.dw.com>

9. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/795702/number-of-agritourism-facilities-in-italy/>

10. https://www.tourismcareers.eu/team_type/eurogites/

11. <https://wwoof.net/fowo/>

SMART-МАРКЕТИНГ – КАК АКТИВАТОР ПАРАДИГМЫ «ПРОДВИЖЕНИЕ» В РАЗВИТИИ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ МАРКЕТОЛОГОВ

Курпаяниди Константин Иванович

к.э.н., профессор Российской Академии естествознания,
Ферганский политехнический институт

Аннотация. Одним из важнейших катализаторов радикальных перемен в мировом хозяйстве, которые кардинально изменили, традиционные представления об экономических, политических и культурных ценностях, явились взрывное развитие информационных технологий в тесном переплетении с продолжающейся глобализацией мировой экономики. Это требует адаптации жизни страны к новым способам государственного управления, ведения бизнеса, предоставления услуг, в том числе таких

важных, как образовательные. В работе рассмотрен SMART-маркетинг в качестве вектора продвижения в развитии профессиональных компетенций маркетологов.

Ключевые слова: глобализация, инновации, маркетинг, smart-маркетинг, управление.

SMART MARKETING – AS AN ACTIVATOR OF THE "PROMOTION" PARADIGM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF MARKETERS

Kurpayanidi Konstantin Ivanovich

Ph.D. in Economics, Professor of the Russian Academy of Natural Sciences,
Fergana Polytechnic Institute

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7423715>

Abstract: One of the most important catalysts of radical changes in the world economy, which radically changed traditional ideas about economic, political and cultural values, was the explosive development of information technologies in close intertwining with the ongoing globalization of the world economy. This requires adapting the life of the country to new ways of public administration, doing business, and providing services, including such important ones as educational. The paper considers SMART marketing as a vector of promotion in the development of professional competencies of marketers.

Keywords: globalization, innovation, marketing, smart marketing, management.

The world economy is developing in conditions of increasing external and internal contradictions, which, on the one hand, are the result of crisis phenomena and processes in the world community and within the country, and on the other, expanding resource constraints caused by the coronavirus pandemic and motivational uncertainty regarding the concentration of efforts of business, government and society on innovative transformations of various scales and levels (modernization, restructuring, organizational and managerial, etc.).

In the process of analytical and experimental studies of the effective export of goods and services, the need to take into account the influence of not only traditional factors, but also the new conflict interaction of key participants and variables of smart business components has been established:

- technological,
- economic,
- investment marketing and others.

This conflict interaction manifests itself in two fundamental trends in ~~the~~ development of the world economy:

1) in the last 15 years, there has been a "mysterious" growth of the world economy and, accordingly, the income of the population by an average of 2-3% with an increase in production volumes in high-tech companies by 6-10%. The established global trend of socio-economic disproportion in the world economy strengthens the market gap between the real demand and supply of goods and services and generates new marketing logistical challenges to traditional technologies of their sales;

2) the technical, technological and functional complexity of the products produced and sold to consumers is characterized by an outstripping growth in relation to the competencies of consumers in the process of their practical use, operation.

The established global technological and functional disproportion in the world economy strengthens the information and communication market gap in the professional and operational interaction of the producer and consumer.

According to the results of a study of the marketing practice of high-tech companies, the goals of current marketing and the tools to achieve them in the conditions of increasing differentiated development of a highly competitive market are constantly changing and dictate the need to adapt to market changes through the development of new priorities of global business and the search for strategic competitive value advantages, the growing digitization of the market environment of "producer-client" interaction.

At the same time, the modern paradigm of "promotion" of traditional goods and services "weakly sees or does not see their customer preferences through the eyes of the customer." As a result, companies do not master and do not satisfy the customer preferences of their customers; as a result, the golden rule of business success is not implemented: "If the producer does not fulfill the customer's request within less than 30 seconds, then a competitor will fulfill it." The key problematic reason for traditional marketing is the gap between the interests of marketers, company managers acting on the basis of the "promotion" paradigm, focused on "cost, price and profit", conversions, sales funnel, profitability, etc., and the interests of the client, for whom the main thing is the ratio of "functional-emotional value and price".

Taking into account the above research, based on traditional marketing, they do not allow to penetrate into the client's thinking. Thus, clients in the survey process mostly formally relate to the questionnaire questions, manipulate their answers in a conversation with an interviewer, or choose a predominantly arbitrary of the proposed answers.

As a result, such information does not allow companies to make proper changes to the production technology and use SMART marketing tools 5P.

The new paradigm of Smart marketing proposed by the authors is aimed at improving the forms of interaction between the manufacturer and the consumer of goods and services based on the implementation of a creative approach from both sides.

In these conditions, a marketer, as one of the professional competencies of a company, needs a wide range of integrated project skills: often market and, of course, skills of project marketing corporate personnel management and a good understanding of the new principles of Smart business and Smart marketing, rather than the traditional business that dominates today.

Marketing, more than other specialties, is subject to constant evolution and constant changes, so interactive training in this specialty is extremely relevant. A marketing specialist throughout his professional life is likely to change jobs many times, and each of them will be formulated with completely different requirements. Moreover, we cannot predict most of these requirements today.

Thus, the proposed Smart marketing requires a completely different approach to the formation of marketing competencies, to the development and implementation of marketing innovations, when the search direction determines not the desire of the marketer or the client, but the change and development of the system of consumer preferences, foresight and design of new requests and needs of people.

References:

1. Kramoliš, J., & Kopečková, M. (2013). Product placement: A smart marketing tool shifting a company to the next competitive level. *Journal of competitiveness*.
2. Simões, D., Barbosa, B., & Filipe, S. (Eds.). (2018). *Smart marketing with the Internet of Things*. IGI Global.
3. Christofi, M., Iaia, L., Marchesani, F., & Masciarelli, F. (2021). Marketing innovation and internationalization in smart city development: a systematic review, framework and research agenda. *International Marketing Review*.
4. Smith, K. T. (2020). Marketing via smart speakers: what should Alexa say? *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 28(4), 350-365.
5. Farooq, M., Cheng, J., Khan, N. U., Saufi, R. A., Kanwal, N., & Bazkiaei, H. A. (2022). Sustainable Waste Management Companies with Innovative Smart Solutions: A Systematic Review and Conceptual Model. *Sustainability*, 14(20), 13146.
6. Reis, J. L., Peter, M. K., Cayolla, R., & Bogdanović, Z. (2021). Marketing and Smart Technologies. *Proceedings of ICMARKTECH*, 1.

З.Зуфарова
ТМИ мустақил изланувчиси

ҲИСОБ СИЁСАТИ АУДИТИНИ ЎТҚАЗИШ БОСҚИЧЛАРИ

Мамлакатимизда барча соҳаларда бўлгани каби аудит соҳасида ҳам кенг қўламли ўзгаришлар амалга оширилиб, аудиторлик фаолиятини халқаро стандартлар талаблари асосида ташкил этишга аҳамият берилмоқда. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг «Аудиторлик фаолияти тўғрисида»ги Қонунининг 32-моддасига мувофиқ, «хўжалик юритувчи субъект молиявий ҳисоботининг ва у билан боғлиқ молиявий ахборотининг аудиторлик

291	<i>Kurpayanidi K.I.</i> SMART MARKETING – AS AN ACTIVATOR OF THE "PROMOTION" PARADIGM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF MARKETERS.....	1025
292	<i>З.Зуфарова.</i> ҲИСОБ СИЁСАТИ АУДИТИНИ ЎТҚАЗИШ БОСҚИЧЛАРИ.....	1027
293	<i>З.Зуфарова.</i> БУХГАЛТЕРИЯ ҲИСОБИ ВА СОЛИҚ ҲИСОБИ БЎЙИЧА ҲИСОБ СИЁСАТИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	1029
294	<i>B.N.Jo'rayev.</i> TURIZM KOMPANIYALARI MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR VA ULARNI BOSHQARISH BOSQICHLARI.....	1031
295	<i>Keldiyorov Bobomurod.</i> IQTISODIY-MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BANK TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH VAZIFALARI.....	1034
296	<i>Баратов С.Н.</i> КАМБАҒАЛЛИККНИ ҚИСҚАРТИРИШДА ИЖТИМОЙ ҲИМОЯ СИЁСАТИНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ АСОСЛАРИ.....	1037
297	<i>M.Ravshanova.</i> PECULIARITIES OF DIGITAL ECONOMY AND ITS DEVELOPMENT TENDENCIES IN THE BANKING SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN.....	1040
298	<i>M.Ravshanova, Allayarov Sh.</i> INNOVATIONS IN BANKING SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN: DIGITAL BANKING AND ITS ADVANTAGES.....	1042
299	<i>Авлокулов А.З.</i> ИННОВАЦИОН ФОЙДА НАЗАРИЯСИГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР.....	1044